

CAUSATION

International Journal of Science

Glyphosate And Non Hodgkin Lymphoma: No Causal Relationship II

Research article

Ilija Barukčić¹

¹ Internist, Horandstrasse, 26441 Jever, Germany

* **Correspondence:** E-Mail: Barukcic@t-online.de;
Tel: +49-4466-333; Fax: +49-4466-333.

Impressum:

CAUSATION

International Journal Of Science

Chief-Editor / V. i. S. d. P.:

Ilija Barukčić

Hegelitzer Str. 22

DE-26409 Wittmund-Ardorf (Germany)

© Editorial Team: **EDITORIAL TEAM**

🌐 Website: WWW.CAUSATION.EU

✉ E-Mail: editor@causation.eu

☎ Phone: +(49) 4466 - 333

Year: 2024; Volume: 19; Issue: 3; pp. 5–35.

✉ Received: February 19, 2023

✓ Accepted: March 5, 2023

📅 Published: March 5, 2023

📄 Deutsche Nationalbibliothek Frankfurt

📄 ISSN: 1863-9542

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.7699650

🔍 Find in: [Zenodo](#) [Orcid](#) [Academia ...](#)

Abstract**BACKGROUND:**

The relationship between past, present and future is full of contradictions. A basic question may be asked. Does the transition from the past to the present automatically suspend all laws of nature?

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

A narrative style has been used.

RESULTS:

The thesis without Glyphosate, no Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma is false.

CONCLUSION:

Glyphosate is neither a cause nor the cause of Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma.

Keywords:

Glyphosate; Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

☺ Reviewer 1: None/Author.

☺ Reviewer 2: None.

☺ Reviewer 3: None.

1. Introduction

Theoretically, circumstances are thinkable, under which the conviction of the correctness of something which is objectively false rises and becomes uncorrectable. To push it to the extreme, an author who believes to be the smartest author of all time, is probably just living in the wrong time. In point of fact, it is very easy that an author is convinced that he or she knows all the answers, especially as long as he or she has not been asked all the questions. We are all mortal, and so is possibly the meaning of our theories and knowledge. How sure can we be about this? More or less, it is always useful, every day anew, to consider the consequences¹ of the own and sometimes wrong thinking for an individual and for the human society. Our human experience teaches us in the end that we have probably always been devotees of at least two truths, whereby our conviction of the correctness of the second truth began when we realized that our first truth was wrong. However, how can we recognize a false insight as such and change one's attitude out of oneself and without an urge from another, for sure? In our everyday competition for an everlasting truth, there are probably countless notes on something which is false. An intelligent human being considers thousands of things and chances as much as possible, while a stupid person prefers to consider only one. Nonetheless, even the one who refutes a big mountain of logical fallacies, has to begin by taking a first small step. In the final analysis we must nevertheless state that there is only one note on something which is true, something which is true, is true. Therefore, among those events, things and processes et cetera which do not repeat themselves so often in our hunt for the truth are unique opportunities, time itself and might be other things too. We all know that a rough and ugly stone cannot be polished into a precious gem without repeated friction. Nor human knowledge perfected without repeated trial and fail. For this reason, it would make very little sense to waste time, to miss valuable opportunities, and to fail to choose the right words.

¹Kong-Futzi. (1910). The analects of Confucius. Editor William Edward (1861-1935). Fukuin Printing Company. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7654356>.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

2.1.1. Gaseous oxygen and human life

It was like this, it is like this, and it will remain like this: human beings must breathe gaseous oxygen (see Priestley, 1775) in order to survive. In the absence of sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen, we cannot find a single human being which can live for more than a few minutes, ($p(c_t) = 0$). In point of fact, in the absence of sufficient quantities of gaseous oxygen, human life comes to an end within minutes ($p(d_t)$). In contrast to this, in the presence of sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen, human life does not last forever ($p(b_t)$). Without gaseous oxygen, humans die ($p(d_t)$). But, humans die even in the presence of sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen ($p(b_t)$). When we consider all these remarks accurately enough, can there be any relationship between gaseous oxygen and human life at all?

Table 1. Gaseous oxygen and human life

		Humans alive B_t		
		YES	NO	
Gaseous oxygen	YES	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
A_t	NO	$p(c_t) = 0$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

Despite all doubts and drawbacks, there is a clear relationship between gaseous oxygen and human life. **Without** sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen, **no** human life. A sufficient amount of gaseous oxygen is a necessary condition of human life. In other words, gaseous oxygen is a *conditio sine qua non* (Barukčić, 2021a,b) of human life. Thus far, what secured insights of general kind (see table 1) can we draw from these confirmed knowledge? Nowadays, as well as before, human beings get the gaseous oxygen they need by breathing through their mouth and nose into their lungs. An oxygen level below 19.5 percent is considered oxygen-deficient and immediately dangerous to human life or health. Various adverse health effects will occur, when the level of gaseous oxygen drops below 19.5 percent oxygen. At concentrations of 16 to 19.5 percent of gaseous oxygen, increased breathing rates, accelerated heartbeat and impaired coordination or thinking might occur in people who are not resting. Concentrations of gaseous oxygen of 12 to 16 percent oxygen cause increased breathing rates, accelerated heartbeat, and impaired coordination et cetera even in people who are resting. At gaseous oxygen levels of 10 to 14 percent, exhaustion, faulty judgment and intermittent respiration is observed even with minimal exertion. Breathing air containing 6 to 10 percent of gaseous oxygen results in lethargic movements, nausea, vomiting and perhaps unconsciousness. Breathing air containing less than 6 percent of gaseous oxygen produces cessation of breathing, followed by cardiac standstill. These symptoms occur immediately.²

²Briehl MM. Oxygen in human health from life to death—An approach to teaching redox biology and signaling to graduate and medical students. *Redox Biol.* 2015 Aug;5:124-139. doi: 10.1016/j.redox.2015.04.002. PMID: 25912168; PMCID: PMC4412967.

2.2. Methods

Avoiding and treatment of logical fallacies addresses one of the most important aspects of any scientific inquiry. Sometimes logically sound definitions are of great help in order to enable us to properly infer **from something known to something unknown**. It also goes without any need of further saying that a definition as such should be logically consistent and correct. However, theoretically, circumstances might exist under which it is required to *deal with erroneous definitions*³ too.

2.2.1. Conditio sine qua non relationship

The probability of the necessary condition relationship $p(\text{SINE})$ has been calculated (Barukčić, 2021a,b) and tested for statistical significance. The chi-square goodness of fit test $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | B)$ and $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | \underline{A})$ with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit the theoretical distribution of a necessary condition relationship in the population. Additionally, the P Value has been calculated approximately (see also Barukčić, 2019c). The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2016, 2020, 2021b) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events. The cumulative, right-tailed hyper-geometric (Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided right-tailed significance of the causal relationship k . As known, a negative causal relationship ($k < 0$) would contradict a necessary condition relationship and vice versa.

2.2.2. Hyper-geometric distribution

In general, the probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable X is called a hyper-geometric distribution. In contrast to the binomial distribution, the hyper-geometric distribution is characterised by the lack of replacements. In this context, let N denote the population size, let A denote the number of success in the population, let B denote the number of draws (i.e. quantity drawn in each trial), let a itself denote the number of observed successes.

Table 2. Hyper-geometric random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	a	b	A
	A_t	FALSE	c	<u>d</u>
		B	<u>B</u>	N

With this in mind, the probability mass function of the hyper-geometric distribution (see Fisher,

³Strobino, Riccardo, "Ibn Sina's Logic", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Fall 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2018/entries/ibn-sina-logic/>.

1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899), denoted as $p(X = a)$, is defined as

$$p(X = a) = \frac{\binom{A}{a} \binom{N-A}{B-a}}{\binom{N}{B}} = \frac{\binom{B}{a} \binom{N-B}{A-a}}{\binom{N}{A}} \quad (1)$$

The hyper-geometric distribution, a probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable, has several properties which unfortunately cannot be discussed in detail here. A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is greater than or equal to some specified lower limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (2)$$

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is less than or equal to some specified upper limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^a \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (3)$$

2.2.3. Fisher's exact test

Fisher's exact test proposed by Fisher (1934) in the fifth edition of *Statistical Methods for Research Workers* (see Fisher, 1934, pp. 99-103) is a statistical significance test which is often used in the analysis of contingency tables while applying the hyper-geometric distribution⁴. This statistical methodology opens up the possibility to calculate the significance of the deviation from a null hypothesis (e.g., P Value) exactly. Strangely enough, it is common practice to use Fisher's exact test (see also Fisher, 1935) for a sample which is very small. However, it is necessary to point out that Fisher's exact test is valid for all sample sizes without any restriction. Fisher's Exact Test is using the following null and alternative hypotheses:

H0: (null hypothesis)

The two random variables are independent.

H1: (alternative hypothesis)

⁴Kim HY. Statistical notes for clinical researchers: Chi-squared test and Fisher's exact test. *Restor Dent Endod.* 2017 May;42(2):152-155. doi: 10.5395/rde.2017.42.2.152. Epub 2017 Mar 30. PMID: 28503482; PMCID: PMC5426219.

The two random variables are not independent.

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability denotes whether a hyper-geometric random variable is greater than or equal to some specified lower limit and less than or equal to some specified upper limit. The P Value of an one-sided right tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{i=a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (4)$$

The P Value of an one-sided left tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=a} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (5)$$

2.2.4. The Chi-square goodness of fit test

The χ^2 distribution is one of the most versatile distributions in applied statistics. Historically, the χ^2 distribution has been described by the German statistician Friedrich Robert Helmert (see [Helmert, 1876](#)). Later, the χ^2 distribution has been rediscovered by Karl Pearson (see [Pearson, 1900](#)) in the context of a goodness of fit test. The Chi-square goodness of fit test checks the agreement or conformity or consistency between a hypothetical or a theoretical distribution given in a population and a sample distribution drawn from such a population. Karl Pearson's approximate formula for calculating a Chi-square statistic may be shown schematically as:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{(\text{Observed}_t - E(\text{Observed}_t))^2}{E(\text{Observed}_t)} \quad (6)$$

Some author prefer the use of Yate's correction for continuity (see [Yates, 1934](#)) when there is one degree of freedom.

Example

Let us illustrate the Chi-square goodness of fit test by an example. A random sample of 100 people with 44 men and 56 women is drawn from a certain population. It is assumed that men and women are equal in frequency in the population. The theoretical frequencies of 50 men and 50 women is compared with the observed number of men and women.

Bernoulli trial t	Event	Observed O_t	Expected $E(O_t)$	$(O_t - E(O_t))^2$	$(O_t - E(O_t))^2 / E(O_t)$
1	Men	44	50	36	0.72
2	Women	56	50	36	0.72
Rows = 2		Sample size =	100	Chi-square =	1.44

There are rows - 1 = 2 - 1 = 1 degree of freedom and for $\alpha = 5$ percent level of significance, the rejection region is $\chi^2 \geq 3.84$. A $\chi^2 = 1.44$ is less than 3.84 and not significant. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis: the sample distribution is consistent with a theoretical distribution given in population. In other words, men and women are more or less equal in frequency in the population. In the case of a necessary condition relationship (SINE), our hypotheses could be:

$$H_0: p(\text{SINE}) \geq 1 \text{ vs. } H_A: p(\text{SINE}) < 1$$

However, a probability cannot be greater than 1. Therefore, the hypotheses are more precisely

$$H_0: p(\text{SINE}) = 1 \text{ vs. } H_A: p(\text{SINE}) < 1$$

Accepting H_0 is equivalent with rejecting H_A and vice versa. Accepting H_A is equivalent with rejecting H_0 . Assumed that the degree of freedom is 1 and for $\alpha = 5$ percent level of significance, the rejection region is $\chi^2 \geq 3.84$. A χ^2 of a necessary condition relationship which is less than 3.84 is not significant. Therefore, we would have to accept the null hypothesis: a sample distribution would be consistent with a theoretical distribution of a necessary condition relationship given in population. However, Chi-square like any statistics has its limitations. The Chi-square is highly sensitive to sample size. The Chi-square goodness of fit test might give inaccurate results when the sample size is too small ($N < 50$) or too large (see [Bagozzi, 1981](#)) (G-square test). When the sample sizes are too small, Fisher's exact test of independence can be considered too.

2.2.5. The P Value of extreme events

There are circumstances where N Bernoulli trials (see [Uspensky, 1937](#), p. 45) are performed while an event X_t should occur at each single Bernoulli trial t . The probability of a single event is given as

$$p(X_t) = \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t \times p(X_t)}{X_t} \quad (7)$$

The probability of a single anti-event or non-event et cetera is given as

$$p(\bar{X}_t) = 1 - p(X_t) = 1 - \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t}{X_t} - \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - X_t \times p(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t \times (1 - p(X_t))}{X_t} = \frac{E(\bar{X}_t)}{X_t} \quad (8)$$

As soon, as the number of Bernoulli trials increases, the probability of a single event follows approximately (see Barukčić, 2019c, p. 1844) as

$$p(X_t) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{E(X_t)}{N}\right)\right) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{X_t \times (1 - p(X_t))}{N}\right)\right) \quad (9)$$

Under conditions where $X_t = N$, equation 9 simplifies to

$$p(X_t) = \exp(-(1 - p(X_t))) \quad (10)$$

There are single events or relationships where the probability of an event or of a relationship is constant from trial to trial and equals $p(X_t) = 1$ in the population. Nonetheless, for many reasons, such extreme events like the necessary condition relationship, the sufficient condition relationship, the exclusion relationship et cetera does not necessarily have to be given in a sample drawn from a population too. Under these circumstances, there is a need to proof whether there is a significant difference between the sample probability or proportion and the population probability or proportion or is the difference due to chance. In other words, does the sample probability or proportion deviate significantly from the population probability or proportion which itself is equal to 1. We perform a one-sided left tailed statistical test. A probability of a single event cannot be greater than 1, therefore our hypotheses are:

$$H_0: p(X_t) \leq 0.999\ 999 \dots \text{ vs. } H_A: p(X_t) > 0.999\ 999 \dots$$

In general, the expectation value of extreme events or relationship with $p(X_t) = 1$ at every single Bernoulli trial t is $E(X) = N \times p(X_t) = N \times 1 = N$. Thus far, under circumstances where $N = E(X)$, the hypotheses before simplify to

$$H_0: E(X) \leq N-1 \text{ vs. } H_A: E(X) > N-1$$

However, it is to be noted that $N > N-1$. The cumulative distribution function is given as

$$p(E(X_t))\text{cdf} = p(X_t = 0) + p(X_t = 1) + \dots + p(X_t = (N - 1)) + p(X_t = N) = +1 \quad (11)$$

It is

$$p(E(X_t) \leq N - 1) = p(X_t = 0) + p(X_t = 1) + \dots + p(X_t = (N - 1)) \quad (12)$$

and

$$p(E(X_t) > N - 1) = p(E(X_t) = N) \quad (13)$$

The P Value of a one-sided left (see Barukčić, 2019c, p. 1846) tailed statistical test is given as

$$\text{P Value}_{\text{one sided left tailed}} = p(E(X_t) \leq N - 1) = 1 - p(E(X_t) > N - 1) = 1 - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{E(X_t)}{N}\right)\right) \quad (14)$$

We have reasons to believe that a left tailed P Value which is greater than or equal to the significance level α or P Value $\geq \alpha$, is providing some evidence to accept the null hypothesis: The sample distribution deviates significantly from the population distribution. Under such circumstances, the sample data would not support a claim that i.e. there is a significant *conditio sine qua non* relationship or *conditio per quam* relationship or exclusion relationship et cetera. However, a left tailed P Value which is less than the significance level α or P Value $< \alpha$, urges us to reject the null hypothesis and to accept the alternative hypothesis. In other words, there is no deviation of the probability found in a sample distribution from the the probability of a population distribution. It is $p(X_t) = 1$ with a certain P Value.

2.2.6. Bonferroni correction

Multiple testing at a certain level of significance α might amplify the probability of false-positive findings. In other words, the more inferences are made (on a certain data body i. e. subgroup analyses et cetera), the more likely erroneous inferences might realise. At the end, several independent or dependent statistical tests performed simultaneously (on the same data body) can induce the so called family-wise error rate (FWER) or multiple testing problem. The family-wise error rate or multiple testing problem (see [Tukey, 1994](#)) is ascribed to John Wilder Tukey (1915 – 2000), an American mathematician and statistician. The probability that at least one null hypothesis out of k null hypotheses tested is falsely rejected is no longer equal to the overall significance level α but equal to

$$\alpha_{\text{FWER}} = 1 - (1 - \alpha)^k \quad (15)$$

As a consequence, a higher significance threshold for an individual hypothesis, denoted as α_i , is demanded. Various statistical techniques have been developed to address this problem. The Bonferroni multiple-comparison correction (see [Bonferroni, 1936](#); [Dunn, 1961](#)) is one of the solutions proposed to compensate for the number of inferences being made.

Example

An investigation is testing $m = 20$ hypotheses with a desired $\alpha = 0.05$. Under these circumstances, the Bonferroni correction might be of appropriate use. Each individual hypothesis should be tested at a single level of significance α_i given as

$$\alpha_i = \frac{\alpha}{m} = \frac{0,05}{20} = 0,0025 \quad (16)$$

where m is the total number hypotheses tested and α is the overall significance level. By requiring a stricter significance threshold, **an inflation of false positive results** can be prevented. In the context of further scientific development, there have been several trials to improve the Bonferroni method. One of these attempts is the so called Rom's Method published 1990 by Rom (see [Rom, 1990](#)) himself.

2.2.7. Bias

Many times, potential publication bias among the studies is assessed by Begg's funnel plot ^{5, 6, 7, 8} with something like a treatment effect (horizontal axis) and some measure of weight (inverse variance, standard error, sample size et cetera) on the vertical axis. It is not always an easy task to bring various studies together which differ in different aspects in order to re-analyse the same or for doing a meta-analysis. Due to several reasons, variability in the data of the studies and other difference might be

⁵Light RJ, Pillemer DB. Summing up. The science of reviewing research. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1984.

⁶Egger M, Davey Smith G, Schneider M, Minder C. Bias in meta-analysis detected by a simple, graphical test. *BMJ*. 1997 Sep 13;315(7109):629-34. doi: 10.1136/bmj.315.7109.629. PMID: 9310563; PMCID: PMC2127453.

⁷Begg CB, Mazumdar M. Operating characteristics of a rank correlation test for publication bias. *Biometrics*. 1994 Dec;50(4):1088-101. PMID: 7786990.

⁸Lau J, Ioannidis JP, Terrin N, Schmid CH, Olkin I. The case of the misleading funnel plot. *BMJ*. 2006 Sep 16;333(7568):597-600. doi: 10.1136/bmj.333.7568.597. PMID: 16974018; PMCID: PMC1570006.

found. These days the heterogeneity among the studies is assessed through a so called I^2 statistics⁹,¹⁰,¹¹ to. Under usual circumstances, an I^2 value of 25%, 50% and 75% are regarded as low, moderate and high heterogeneity¹². In this investigation, we preferred to control the study (design) bias and the heterogeneity among the studies by IOI, the index of independence (Barukčić, 2019a) and by IOU, the index of unfairness (Barukčić, 2019b).

2.2.8. Sample size

In scientific practice, the truth is not known from the very beginning, but often need to be discovered in arduous detail work. However, under usual circumstances, it is impossible to study an entire population. So this is more or less one of the reasons why studies are conducted on samples drawn from a population and investigated. In the course of further investigations, conclusions are drawn from samples¹³ and generalised to the population. In this regard, a sample as such should be a perfect representative of the population studied, independent of any sample size. It comes therefore as no surprise that a larger sample size might be a better representative of a certain population and will hence provide more accurate results. However, beyond a certain point, an increase in sample size is not worth the effort. In other words, proper methods of study design and sampling should be used while the prevalence of an event within a population can be considered accurately. In this process of insight, there are some mistakes which can occur. Especially, a null hypothesis which is true can incorrectly be rejected and the either way. A null hypothesis which is false can incorrectly be accepted. However, one key aspect when designing an experiment or a clinical study et cetera, is the calculation of an appropriate sample size. A sample size is the number of experimental units or measurements (i.e. the number of patients in a medical study) et cetera needed to be included into a study in order to answer a certain research question. Therefore, an accurate pre-study calculation of the sample size¹⁴ is of great importance. Nonetheless, it is worthy of attention that methods to calculate the sample size which are explained in statistical textbooks in more detail are prone to errors and changes in the selected parameters can lead to significant differences in the sample size. In fact, our experience so far has taught us, that a sample size which is too small, is tending to make it impossible to detect any difference or effect. In complete contrast to a small sample size, a sample that is larger than necessary might be a better representative of a certain population and may provide more accurate results. However, beyond a certain point, a sample that is too large may amplify differences and induce a waste of time and money. Thus far, are large studies really more reliable than smaller studies, are smaller studies completely worthless? Despite of

⁹Cochran WG. The combination of estimates from different experiments. *Biometrics* 1954; 10(1): 101-29.

¹⁰Higgins JP, Thompson SG. Quantifying heterogeneity in a meta-analysis. *Stat Med*. 2002 Jun 15;21(11):1539-58. doi: 10.1002/sim.1186. PMID: 12111919.

¹¹Higgins JP, Thompson SG, Deeks JJ, Altman DG. Measuring inconsistency in meta-analyses. *BMJ*. 2003 Sep 6;327(7414):557-60. doi: 10.1136/bmj.327.7414.557. PMID: 12958120; PMCID: PMC192859.

¹²Higgins JP, Thompson SG, Deeks JJ, Altman DG. Measuring inconsistency in meta-analyses. *BMJ*. 2003 Sep 6;327(7414):557-60. doi: 10.1136/bmj.327.7414.557. PMID: 12958120; PMCID: PMC192859.

¹³Faber J, Fonseca LM. How sample size influences research outcomes. *Dental Press J Orthod*. 2014 Jul-Aug;19(4):27-9. doi: 10.1590/2176-9451.19.4.027-029.ebo. PMID: 25279518; PMCID: PMC4296634.

¹⁴Hickey GL, Grant SW, Dunning J, Siepe M. Statistical primer: sample size and power calculations-why, when and how? *Eur J Cardiothorac Surg*. 2018 Jul 1;54(1):4-9. doi: 10.1093/ejcts/ezy169. PMID: 29757369; PMCID: PMC6005113.

all the incontestable benefits of studies with a large sample size, a variety of biases¹⁵ of studies with large sample size like measurement error, aggregation error, sampling error, multiple comparisons errors et cetera have been identified. In point of fact, studies with a large sample size can magnify the bias associated with error resulting from study design or sampling and so on. The issue of sample size is more or less not as simple as is often desired or assumed. Alongside undeniable scientific progress supported by studies, there are shortcomings and obvious delays and a particular caution and constant watchfulness and reserve is necessary, independently of the sample size of a study. In principle, even studies with a small sample size can play an important role in helping us recognise a certain relationship between events. Thus far and for illustration purposes only, let us suppose that a small study is investigating the relationship between gaseous oxygen and human being alive. Only three subjects were investigated, the following data were obtained and published.

Table 3. Gaseous oxygen and human being alive

		Human being alive B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Gaseous oxygen A_t	TRUE	1	1	2
	FALSE	0	1	1
		1	2	3

Are the results of such a study completely irrelevant? Under normal circumstances, our confidence into a relationship identified is running high, parallel with an increasing sample size. In contrast to a very large sample size, even a study with a very small sample size ($N = 3$) or even one single study is capable of identifying a fundamental relationship i.e. between gaseous oxygen and human life, it depends as always on the concrete circumstances. Human experience teaches us however that the relationship between gaseous oxygen and human life as established before is true even if the sample size of the study presented is very small. As is well known, it is rarely possible to study the entire population. Nonetheless, further studies despite a larger sample size must be able to confirm the relationship established before in principle, independently of any potential difficulties.

Type I Error (Alpha)

The type I error is also called alpha or the significance level or the P Value and represents the chance or the probability to decide that two groups investigated differ while in reality these two groups do not differ. In other words, it is the chance or the probability of a false-positive conclusion. Under usual circumstances, alpha is fixed at 0.05, which indicates that a researcher desires a less than 5% chance of drawing a false-positive conclusion. The conclusion drawn is false, because positive. The P Value is the probability obtained of incorrectly accepting the alternate hypothesis. The P Value is compared to the the significance level α to determine whether the result is statistically significant. The lower the P Value, the lower the probability of obtaining that result if a null hypothesis were true.

¹⁵Kaplan RM, Chambers DA, Glasgow RE. Big data and large sample size: a cautionary note on the potential for bias. *Clin Transl Sci.* 2014 Aug;7(4):342-6. doi: 10.1111/cts.12178. Epub 2014 Jul 15. PMID: 25043853; PMCID: PMC5439816.

Type I and type II errors

Type I error: A true null hypothesis is rejected. **Type II error:** A false null hypothesis is accepted.

Figure 1. Today's understanding of the relationship between Type I error and Type II error.

Power (1-Beta)

The type II error is also called beta and represents the chance or the probability to decide that the two groups investigated do not differ (no difference), while in reality these two groups do differ. In other words, it is the chance or the probability of a false-negative conclusion. The conclusion drawn is false, because negative. Usually, beta is set at a level of 0.20. In other words, a researcher desires a less than 20% chance of a false-negative conclusion. Nonetheless, for the calculation of the sample size, it is necessary to consider the following relationship.

$$\beta + \text{power} = 1 \quad (17)$$

Consequently, power is the complement of beta, i.e. $\text{power} = 1 - \beta$. Thus far, if beta is 0.20, then the power is 0.80 or 80%. The power indicates the probability or the chance to avoid a false-negative conclusion or, in other words, the probability to detect a specified effect, assumed that the same really exists.

What is very interesting is that today's understanding of the relationship between Type I error and Type II error excludes the possibility of a joint distribution between Type I error and Type II error, as demonstrated by figure ¹⁶ 1. In other words, theoretically, it appears not to be possible that a null-

¹⁶Serdar CC, Cihan M, Yücel D, Serdar MA. Sample size, power and effect size revisited: simplified and practical approaches in

hypothesis is false in reality (α) and that a statistical test tell us at the same time that a null-hypothesis is false (β) too. In the long run, this shortcoming may turn out to be unsustainable.

Table 4. Today's relationship between α and β

		R E S E A R C H		
		H ₀ is TRUE	H _A is TRUE	
R E A L I T Y	H ₀ is TRUE	$1 - \alpha$	α	1
	H _A is TRUE	β	$1 - \beta$	1
		$1 - \alpha + \beta$	$1 + \alpha - \beta$	2

pre-clinical, clinical and laboratory studies. *Biochem Med (Zagreb)*. 2021 Feb 15;31(1):010502. doi: 10.11613/BM.2021.010502. Epub 2020 Dec 15. PMID: 33380887; PMCID: PMC7745163.

3. Results

3.1. Theorem. Without gaseous oxygen, no human life.

In general, the thesis **without** gaseous oxygen, **no** human life, is known and acknowledged as generally accepted human knowledge. However, the way to this point was long.

Theorem 1 (Without gaseous oxygen, no human life.). *If A_t (i.e. gaseous oxygen) is a necessary condition of B_t (i.e. humans alive) today and if B_t (i.e. humans alive) did exist in the past, then the same event A_t (i.e. gaseous oxygen) must-have been a necessary condition in the past too, otherwise B_t (i.e. humans alive) cannot have existed in the past, or we are no longer talking about the same A_t (i.e. humans alive).*

Proof by direct proof. Our axiom or the thesis **without** gaseous oxygen, **no** human life is true. What are the consequences? However, this thesis is true today, this thesis has been true in the past and this thesis will be true in the future. Gaseous oxygen as such need not be the cause of human life, too. However, **without** gaseous oxygen, there has not been human life, there is **no** human life and there will not be human life.

Let us assume that investigations (1925-1975) have been performed. In the past (before 1925 or after 1975), it was not possible that human being were alive (B_t) in the absence of gaseous (A_t) oxygen (see Fig. 2). Even today, it is not possible that human being are alive in the absence of gaseous oxygen et cetera. What conclusion may we draw from this? If we are able to observe an event, say B_t or humans are alive at a certain point or Bernoulli trial t , then the necessary condition need to be given too (see Fig. 2), otherwise B_t would not exist. As well, in the past, B_t could not exist without A_t . As a consequence, if A_t is a necessary condition of B_t today and if B_t did exist in the past, then the same event A_t must-have been a necessary condition in the past too.

□

Figure 2. Time and necessary condition.

Active immunity against the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) or coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is not simple to establish. Messenger ribonucleic acid (mRNA) vaccines (see Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2) trial ¹⁷ and Moderna vaccine (mRNA-1273) trial ¹⁸) provide a novel and alternative approach to achieve such a goal. However, it is claimed that serious, even systemic, side effects have been identified in this context ¹⁹ and the safety of these mRNA vaccines is heavily questioned. But where is the truth, and where is the fiction?

¹⁷Polack FP, Thomas SJ, Kitchin N, Absalon J, Gurtman A, Lockhart S, Perez JL, Pérez Marc G, Moreira ED, Zerbini C, Bailey R, Swanson KA, Roychoudhury S, Koury K, Li P, Kalina WV, Cooper D, Frenck RW Jr, Hammitt LL, Türeci Ö, Nell H, Schaefer A, Ünal S, Tresnan DB, Mather S, Dormitzer PR, Şahin U, Jansen KU, Gruber WC; C4591001 Clinical Trial Group. Safety and Efficacy of the BNT162b2 mRNA Covid-19 Vaccine. *N Engl J Med.* 2020 Dec 31;383(27):2603-2615. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2034577. Epub 2020 Dec 10. PMID: 33301246; PMCID: PMC7745181.

¹⁸Baden LR, El Sahly HM, Essink B, Kotloff K, Frey S, Novak R, Diemert D, Spector SA, Rouphael N, Creech CB, McGettigan J, Khetan S, Segall N, Solis J, Brosz A, Fierro C, Schwartz H, Neuzil K, Corey L, Gilbert P, Janes H, Follmann D, Marovich M, Mascola J, Polakowski L, Ledgerwood J, Graham BS, Bennett H, Pajon R, Knightly C, Leav B, Deng W, Zhou H, Han S, Ivarsson M, Miller J, Zaks T; COVE Study Group. Efficacy and Safety of the mRNA-1273 SARS-CoV-2 Vaccine. *N Engl J Med.* 2021 Feb 4;384(5):403-416. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2035389. Epub 2020 Dec 30. PMID: 33378609; PMCID: PMC7787219.

¹⁹Anand P, Stahel VP. Review the safety of Covid-19 mRNA vaccines: a review. *Patient Saf Surg.* 2021 May 1;15(1):20. doi: 10.1186/s13037-021-00291-9. Erratum in: *Patient Saf Surg.* 2021 May 18;15(1):22. PMID: 33933145; PMCID: PMC8087878.

3.2. *Theorem. Without Glyphosate, no Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma is false.*

Theorem 2 (Glyphosate and Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma). *The thesis without Glyphosate, no Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma is false. Therefore, there it is not possible that there is a cause effect relationship between Glyphosate and Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma.*

Proof by direct proof. Decades ago in the past, Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma did exist. However, at this time, Glyphosate was not given. In other words, Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma could exist without Glyphosate. Considering theorem 1, it is not possible that Glyphosate is a necessary condition of Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma. If Glyphosate were a necessary condition of Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma today, then the same Glyphosate needs to have been a necessary condition of Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma in the past too. However, in the past (decades ago), this has not been the case. Therefore, even today, Glyphosate cannot be a necessary condition of Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma. However, since Glyphosate is not at least a necessary condition of Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma, it doesn't make any sense to reason about a cause-and-effect relationship between Glyphosate and Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma at all.

□

Figure 3 is illustrating this relationship in more detail. Before the year 1975 neither the condition nor the conditioned (d_t) existed. This does not contradict the necessary condition relationship. After 2000 the condition (A_t) was given and the conditioned (B_t) did exist (coincidence of A_t and B_t).

Figure 3. Time and necessary condition.

Glyphosate or N-(phosphonomethyl)glycine is a broad-spectrum herbicide discovered by Monsanto chemist John E. Franz in 1970 (US Patent 3,799,758). Glyphosate was brought to market in 1974 by Monsanto® under the trade name Roundup®. These relationships are illustrated by figure 4.

Figure 4. Glyphosate and Non Hodgkin Lymphoma.

As can be seen, between 1974 and 2023, the condition (A_t) was given and the conditioned (B_t) was given too. This coincidence of A_t and B_t do support the possibility of a necessary condition relationship between A_t and B_t . However, this fact does not prove the existence of a necessary condition between A_t and B_t at all. If we relied only on this simple fact, we would commit the so-called ‘**cum hoc ergo propter hoc**’ logical fallacy or in ordinary language: B_t together with A_t , therefore because of A_t . Nonetheless, it is not possible to advance one single argument to deny the fact that before the years 1970-1974 Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma did exist while Glyphosate did not exist. This simple historical and equally very heavy weighting fact provide us with an unrefutable evidence that B_t (or Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma) can occur without the existence of A_t (Glyphosate). In other words, A_t (or Glyphosate) is not a necessary condition of B_t (or Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma). A necessary condition is defined and determined by the fact that a conditioned (B_t) cannot exist in the absence of the condition (A_t), it doesn't matter whether in the past or in the present or in the future. In the period before the years 1970-1974, however, it is possible to establish evidence that cannot be refuted that the conditioned (B_t) did exist without the existence of the condition (A_t). In other words, the condition (A_t) was not necessary for the existence of the conditioned (B_t). In conclusion, such a historical fact provides strong enough evidence that A_t is not a necessary condition of B_t (see figure 4). In brief, in order to be able to convince the reader that A_t is potentially causally related to something like B_t , an author needs to provide verifiable proof that the requirements of a necessary condition between A_t and B_t are met or can be met at least theoretically. Without any possible doubt, we have been able to establish clear logical evidence, that Glyphosate (A_t) is not a necessary condition of Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma (B_t). The inevitable logical conclusion is that it does not make any sense to think even for the sake of the argument about the possibility of a cause effect relationship between A_t and B_t .

3.3. *Theorem. Without mRNA vaccination, no myocarditis is false.*

Theorem 3 (mRNA vaccination and myocarditis). *The thesis without mRNA vaccination, no myocarditis is false. Therefore, there it is not possible that there is a cause effect relationship between mRNA vaccination and myocarditis.*

Proof by direct proof. Decades ago in the past, myocarditis did exist. However, at this time, mRNA vaccination was not given. In other words, myocarditis could exist without mRNA vaccination. Considering theorem 1, it is not possible that mRNA vaccination is a necessary condition of myocarditis. If mRNA vaccination were a necessary condition of myocarditis today, then the same mRNA vaccination needs to have been a necessary condition of myocarditis in the past too. However, in the past (decades ago), this has not been the case. Therefore, even today, mRNA vaccination cannot be a necessary condition of myocarditis. However, since mRNA vaccination is not at least a necessary condition of myocarditis, it doesn't make any sense to reason about a cause-and-effect relationship between mRNA vaccination and myocarditis at all.

□

Figure 5. Time and sufficient condition I.

3.4. *Theorem. If mRNA vaccination, then myocarditis is false.*

We have been able to prove that a mRNA vaccination is not a necessary condition of myocarditis. At this point, we would like to prove, whether a mRNA vaccine could be a sufficient condition of myocarditis. The typical characteristics of a sufficient condition are shown by figure 5. It is noticeable that the conditioned (B_t) is given even under circumstances where the condition (A_t) itself is not given (period of time c_t). However, it can equally be seen, that the conditioned (B_t) has to occur in the presence (period of time: a_t) of the condition (A_t). Nevertheless, how do we have to treat the circumstance where the condition (A_t) is given, but the conditional (B_t) itself is not (see fig. 6) observable (period of time: b_t).

Figure 6. Time and sufficient condition II.

Figure 6 contradicts the possibility of a sufficient condition relationship between (A_t) and (B_t).

Theorem 4 (COVID-19 mRNA vaccine and myocarditis). *In general, a Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) mRNA vaccination is not a sufficient condition of myocarditis.*

Proof by direct proof. The hypothesis: **if** COVID-19 mRNA vaccination, **then** myocarditis could be true. However, in this case, it is not allowed to observe one single subject which has been vaccinated by COVID-19 mRNA vaccine but do not suffer from myocarditis (see figure 6, period of time: b_t). The reality, however, convinces us every day anew of the opposite of this hypothesis.

□

3.5. *Theorem. If (COVID-19 mRNA vaccination and at the same time other specific factors), then myocarditis.*

Every human being is different, and not even a pair of twins are perfectly alike. More or less, the individuality of people may be a fact. However, it is necessary to consider theorem 13, p.26²⁰ or the logical equivalence of

$$((A_t \wedge C_t \dots) \vee B_t) = ((A_t \vee B_t) \vee ((C_t \dots) \vee B_t)) = +1 \quad (18)$$

in this context. Independently of this fact, if a condition (A_t) is a necessary condition of the conditioned (B_t), then the conditioned (B_t) will not occur even if there are other specific factors given, if the condition (A_t) itself is not given. Table 5 illustrates the issue of specific factors, denoted by $C_t \dots$, in more detail from another point of view.

Table 5. Compound conditio per quam conditionals

Bernoulli trial	A_t	$C_t \dots$	B_t	$(A_t \wedge C_t \dots)$	$(A_t \wedge C_t \dots)$	$(A_t \vee C_t \dots)$	$(A_t \vee B_t)$	$(C_t \dots \vee B_t)$	$((A_t \wedge C_t \dots) \vee B_t)$	$((A_t \vee B_t) \vee (C_t \dots))$
t	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
2	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
4	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
5	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
6	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1
7	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
8	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
...
$\Sigma=8$	4	4	4	2	6	6	6	6	7	7

Under these circumstances (see table 5, column 9 and column 10), it is necessary to accept the logical equivalence

$$((A_t \wedge C_t \dots) \vee B_t) = ((A_t \vee B_t) \vee (C_t \dots)) \quad (19)$$

In other words, the thesis: **if** (COVID-19 mRNA vaccination and at the same time additional, specific conditions $C_t \dots$), **then** myocarditis is logically equivalent with the claim: **without** the secured relationship **if** (COVID-19 mRNA vaccination), **then** myocarditis²¹ **no** relevance of specific additional conditions $C_t \dots$. Indeed, additional individual factors $C_t \dots$ cannot be ignored and do matter. However, the importance of additional individual factors $C_t \dots$ may not be overestimated. In accordance with equation 19, it is necessary that the relationship

$$(A_t \vee B_t) = 1 \quad (20)$$

²⁰Barukčić, Ilija. (2023). Single and compound conditions. *Causation*, 18(10), 5–34. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7535107>

²¹Schwab C, Domke LM, Hartmann L, Stenzinger A, Longerich T, Schirmacher P. Autopsy-based histopathological characterization of myocarditis after anti-SARS-CoV-2-vaccination. *Clin Res Cardiol*. 2022 Nov 27;1–10. doi: 10.1007/s00392-022-02129-5. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 36436002; PMCID: PMC9702955.

is given, independent of any additional factors $C_t \dots$. In fact, everyday experience shows that neither COVID-19 mRNA vaccination lead to myocarditis nor does Glyphosate lead to NHL, independent of any additional individual factors $C_t \dots$.

3.6. Real-World example

A simple real-world experiment may illustrate the necessary condition relationship and the sufficient condition relationship. Let A_t denote gaseous oxygen, a Binomial random variable, which can take only two values, either gaseous oxygen present = +1 or gaseous oxygen not present = +0. Gaseous oxygen is present means that the amount of gaseous oxygen is enough to assure that a candle made out of wax can burn. Let B_t denote a candle made out of wax, a Binomial random variable, which can take only two values, either a candle is burning $B_t = +1$ or a candle is not burning $B_t = +0$. In this experiment, an investigator lights the candle wick of some candles (old, you, big, small, red, green, curved, straight et cetera) under different conditions. As next, candle flame reacts with gaseous oxygen such that light and heat which characterizes a candle are produced. The data as obtained by this real world experiment are illustrated by the following 2x2 table and support the everyday experience **without** gaseous oxygen, **no** burning candle.

Table 6. Example. Necessary condition

		Candle is burning	
		YES	NO
Gaseous oxygen	YES	+1	+1
	NO	+0	+1
			+1

Another study group investigated the relationship between human pulse rate ≥ 100 , denoted by $C_t \dots$, and gaseous oxygen, denoted by B_t . The relationship between gaseous oxygen and increased human pulse rate is presented by table 7. The necessary condition, **without** gaseous oxygen, **no** human pulse rate ≥ 100 is assured.

Table 7. Example. Necessary condition

		Human pulse rate ≥ 100	
		YES	NO
Gaseous oxygen	YES	+1	+1
	NO	+0	+1
			+1

This result is of course logical too, because without gaseous oxygen, no human life and therefore,

no human pulse rate ≥ 100 . Another study group found evidence of the relationship **without** gaseous oxygen, **no** ((human pulse rate ≥ 100) or (burning candle)).

Table 8. Conditio sine qua non

Bernoulli trial	A_t	$C_t \dots$	B_t	$(B_t \wedge C_t \dots)$	$(B_t \vee C_t \dots)$	$(A_t \vee B_t)$	$(A_t \vee C_t \dots)$	$(A_t \vee (B_t \wedge C_t \dots))$	$((A_t \vee B_t) \vee (A_t \vee C_t \dots))$	$((A_t \vee B_t) \wedge ((A_t) \vee C_t \dots))$	$(A_t \vee (B_t \vee C_t \dots))$
t	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
3	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
4	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
5	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0
7	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0
8	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
...
$\Sigma = 8$	4	4	4	2	6	6	6	7	7	7	7

Table 8 provide us with the necessary formal-logical background. In general, we have to accept the logical equivalence of the relationship (see table 8, column 10 and column 11)

$$(A_t \vee (B_t \vee C_t \dots)) = ((A_t \vee B_t) \wedge ((A_t) \vee C_t \dots)) \quad (21)$$

In the same context, the following logical equivalence (see truth table 8, column 8 and column 9) is given too.

$$(A_t \vee (B_t \wedge C_t \dots)) = ((A_t \vee B_t) \vee (A_t \vee C_t \dots)) \quad (22)$$

In other words, the claim **without** gaseous oxygen, **no** ((human pulse rate ≥ 100) and no (burning candle)) is true. However, as much as the previous relationships may apply, view other aspects need to be considered in more detail. It is known that the converse of the implication $A_t \rightarrow B_t$ may be written as $B_t \rightarrow A_t$. What will follow now should not be mixed up with a converse relationship or with a contrapositive relationship or with an inverse relationship. Disjunctions like $((A_t) \vee (B_t))$ are commutative. In general, $((A_t) \vee (B_t))$ has the same truth value as $((B_t) \vee (A_t))$. As next, we consider the consequences of the general validity of the following logical equivalence

$$((A_t) \vee (B_t)) = ((B_t) \vee (A_t)) \quad (23)$$

by real world examples (see table 9 and table 10).

Table 9. Without gaseous oxygen, no burning candle

	Burning candle		A_t
	TRUE	FALSE	
Gaseous oxygen	TRUE	a_t	B_t
	FALSE	$c_t = 0$	\underline{A}_t
		B_t	\underline{B}_t
			+1

Table 10. If burning candle, then gaseous oxygen

	Gaseous oxygen		B_t
	TRUE	FALSE	
Burning candle	TRUE	a_t	B_t
	FALSE	b_t	\underline{B}_t
		A_t	\underline{A}_t
			+1

It is equally true (see table 11 and table 12) that

Table 11. Without gaseous oxygen, no human pulse rate ≥ 100

		Human pulse rate ≥ 100		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Gaseous oxygen	TRUE	a_t	b_t	A_t
	FALSE	$c_t = 0$	d_t	$\underline{A_t}$
		$C_t \dots$	$\underline{C_t \dots}$	+1

Table 12. If human pulse rate ≥ 100 , then gaseous oxygen is present

		Gaseous oxygen		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Pulse rate ≥ 100	TRUE	a_t	$c_t = 0$	$C_t \dots$
	FALSE	b_t	d_t	$\underline{C_t \dots}$
		A_t	$\underline{A_t}$	+1

The truth table 13 will provide us with the necessary formal-logical background.

Table 13. Conditio per quam

Bernoulli trial	A_t	$C_t \dots$	B_t	$(B_t \wedge C_t \dots)$	$(B_t \vee C_t \dots)$	$(B_t \vee A_t)$	$(\underline{C_t \dots} \vee A_t)$	$((B_t \wedge C_t \dots) \vee A_t)$	$(B_t \vee A_t) \vee (\underline{C_t \dots} \vee A_t)$	$(B_t \vee A_t) \wedge (\underline{C_t \dots} \vee A_t)$	$((B_t \vee C_t \dots) \vee A_t)$
t	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
3	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
4	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
5	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0
7	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0
8	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
...
$\Sigma = 8$	4	4	4	2	6	6	6	7	7	7	7

Among other, we have to accept the logical equivalence of the relationship (see table 13, column 8 and column 9)

$$((\underline{B_t \wedge C_t \dots}) \vee A_t) = ((\underline{B_t}) \vee (A_t)) \vee ((\underline{C_t \dots}) \vee (A_t)) \quad (24)$$

In the words of an ordinary man, the following can be considered in more detail. **If** ((candle is burning) and (human pulse rate ≥ 100)) is true, **then** gaseous oxygen is present. The correctness of this relationship can be proved everywhere.

What are the consequences?

Thus, if a person complains that a vaccination with an mRNA vaccine (B_t) and at the same time his particular individual properties ($C_t \dots$) have led to myocarditis (A_t), he/she is suffering from $((\underline{B_t \wedge C_t \dots}) \vee A_t) = +1$, then such a person is compelled to provide evidence (see equation 24) that a vaccination with a mRNA vaccine is a sufficient condition of myocarditis $((\underline{B_t}) \vee (A_t)) = +1$ or that the particular individual properties ($C_t \dots$) are a sufficient condition of myocarditis (A_t) $((\underline{C_t \dots}) \vee (A_t)) = +1$. However, the particular individual properties ($C_t \dots$) might include viruses like Coxsackie virus too et cetera and can be a sufficient condition of myocarditis. Independent of this fact, a mRNA vaccine need to be a sufficient condition on its own of myocarditis, which is not the case. Nonetheless, to establish a cause effect relationship between mRNA vaccine and myocarditis, much more than a sufficient condition is necessary. It is necessary to provide evidence of a necessary condition relationship between mRNA vaccine and myocarditis. This should not be so easy. The same with the relationship between glyphosate and NHL.

The truth table 13 is illustrated by table 14 from another point of view.

Table 14. Conditio per quam II

		A _t		
		YES	NO	
(B _t ∧ C _t ...)	YES	a _t	b _t = 0	(B _t ∧ C _t ...)
	(B _t ∧ <u>C_t ...</u>) (<u>B_t</u> ∧ C _t ...) (<u>B_t</u> ∧ <u>C_t ...</u>)	NO	c _t	d _t
		A _t	<u>A_t</u>	1

We cannot here never overdo things if we again draw the attention of the reader to the need to consider the logical equivalence of the conditio per quam relationship (see table 13, column 8 and column 9)

$$((\underline{B_t} \wedge C_t \dots) \vee A_t) = ((\underline{B_t}) \vee (A_t)) \vee ((\underline{C_t} \dots) \vee (A_t)) \quad (25)$$

very precisely. Despite hearing occasionally that there are side effects (i.e. ischaemic stroke, myocarditis et cetera) especially in older people with co-morbidities and frailty who received a mRNA COVID-19 Vaccine²² which are critical to their success, a lot of hard work is needed to establish a verifiable causal relationship between a vaccination and a claimed side effect (see equation 25).

²²Soiza RL, Scicluna C, Thomson EC. Efficacy and safety of COVID-19 vaccines in older people. *Age Ageing*. 2021 Feb 26;50(2):279-283. doi: 10.1093/ageing/afaa274. PMID: 33320183; PMCID: PMC7799251.

4. Discussion

Changes of objective reality require sometimes classifying events as past, present or future. In general, we possess the possibility to use facts in the past in order to emphasize our cognitive or epistemic relationship to the present. What might be the internal relationship between past, present and future? In point of fact, the present might entail something like a negation of the past. However, do we have to accept in principle that something (i.e. A_{t-x} or gaseous oxygen), which has been a necessary condition of something else (i.e. B_{t-x} or humans alive) in the past, is this no longer automatically, as soon as it reaches the present? In the past, oxygen has been a necessary condition of human life. By the power of an act of transition from the past to the present, oxygen would become no longer a necessary condition of human life. In this particular case, what destructive force would such a transition from the past to the present have to possess? Such a picture of objective reality seems to us to be very restrictive and grossly erroneous. In the event that we have knowledge that A_t is a necessary condition of B_t today, this must also have been the case in the past, if B_t as such did exist in the past. Therefore, the reverse conclusion is then also permitted. If B_t has been given in the past without A_t , then even today (the present) B_t will be given without A_t (see theorem 1).

5. Conclusion

‘Glyphosate is neither a cause nor the cause of Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma.’

Acknowledgments

No funding or any financial support by a third party was received.

Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications

does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

References

- Richard P. Bagozzi. Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error: A comment. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(3):375–381, 1981. ISSN 00222437. URL <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3150979>.
- Ilija Barukčić. The Mathematical Formula of the Causal Relationship k. *International Journal of Applied Physics and Mathematics*, 6(2):45–65, January 2016. doi: 10.17706/ijapm.2016.6.2.45-65. [IJAPM](#). Free full text: [IAP](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. Index of Independence. *Modern Health Science*, 2(2):1–25, 10 2019a. ISSN 2576-7305. doi: 10.30560/mhs.v2n2p1. URL <https://j.ideasspread.org/index.php/mhs/article/view/331>. [Modern Health Science](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. Index of Unfairness. *Modern Health Science*, 2(1):22, 4 2019b. ISSN 2576-7305, 2576-7291. doi: 10.30560/mhs.v2n1p22. [Modern Health Science](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. The P Value of likely extreme events. *International Journal of Current Science Research*, 5(11):1841–1861, 2019c. [IJCSR ZENODO](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. Causal relationship k. *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology IJMTT*, 66(10):76–115, 2020. URL <http://www.ijmttjournal.org/archive/ijmtt-v66i10p512>. [IJMTT](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. Mutually exclusive events. *Causation*, 16(11):5–57, November 2021a. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5746415. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5746415>. [Zenodo](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. The causal relationship k. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 336:09032, 2021b. ISSN 2261-236X. doi: 10.1051/mateconf/202133609032. [CSCNS2020](#). [Web of Science](#). Free full text: [EDP Sciences](#).
- Carlo Emilio Bonferroni. Teoria statistica delle classi e calcolo delle probabilita. *Pubblicazioni del R Istituto Superiore di Scienze Economiche e Commerciali di Firenze*, 8:3–62, 1936.
- Olive Jean Dunn. Multiple comparisons among means. *Journal of the American statistical association*, 56(293):52–64, 1961.
- Ronald Aylmer Fisher. On the Interpretation of Chi square from Contingency Tables, and the Calculation of P. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society*, 85(1):87–94, 1922. ISSN 0952-8385. doi: 10.2307/2340521. [JSTOR](#).
- Ronald Aylmer Fisher. *Statistical methods for research workers*. Number 5 in Biological Monographs and manuals. Oliver and Boyd, Edinburgh, 1934. [Archive.org](#).
- Sir Ronald Aylmer Fisher. *The Design Of Experiments*. Oliver and Boyd, Edinburgh, 1935.
- H. T. Gonin. XIV. The use of factorial moments in the treatment of the hypergeometric distribution and in tests for regression. *The London, Edinburgh, and Dublin Philosophical Magazine and Journal of Science*, 21(139):215–226, January 1936. ISSN 1941-5982. doi: 10.1080/14786443608561573. [Taylor and Francis](#).
- Friedrich Robert Helmert. Über die Wahrscheinlichkeit der Potenzsummen der Beobachtungsfehler und über einige damit im Zusammenhange stehende Fragen. *Zeitschrift für Mathematik und Physik*, 21(3):102–219, 1876.
- Christiaan Huygens and Frans van Schooten. *De ratiociniis in ludo alae: In: Exercitationum mathematicarum liber primus [- quintus].* ex officina Johannis Elsevirii, Lugdunum Batavorum (Leiden, The Netherlands), January 1657. doi: 10.3931/e-rara-8813. Free full text: [e-rara](#), [Zurich](#), [CH](#).
- Karl Pearson. XV. On certain properties of the hypergeometrical series, and on the fitting of such series to observation polygons in the theory of chance. *The London, Edinburgh, and Dublin Philosophical Magazine and Journal of Science*, 47(285):236–246, January 1899. ISSN 1941-5982. doi: 10.1080/14786449908621253. [Taylor and Francis](#).
- Karl Pearson. X. On the Criterion that a Given System of Deviations from the Probable in the Case of a Correlated System of Variables is such that it can be Reasonably Supposed to have Arisen from Random Sampling. *The London, Edinburgh, and Dublin Philosophical Magazine and Journal of Science*, 50(302):157–175, 1900.
- Joseph Priestley. Xxxviii. an account of further discoveries in air. by the rev. joseph priestley, ll. dfrs in letters to sir john pringle, bart. prs and the rev. dr. price, frs. *Philosophical Transactions*, 65:384–394, 1775. doi: 10.1098/rstl.1775.0039. [The Royal Society](#).

-
- Dror M Rom. A sequentially rejective test procedure based on a modified bonferroni inequality. *Biometrika*, 77(3):663–665, 1990.
- John Wilder Tukey. *Multiple comparisons: 1948-1983*. In: The collected works of John W. Tukey. Volume VIII. Ed. by Henry I. Braun, with the assistance of Bruce Kaplan, Kathleen M. Sheehan, Min-Hwei Wang. New York, Chapman and Hall, 1994. ISBN 0-412-05121-4.
- J. v. Uspensky. *Introduction To Mathematical Probability*. McGraw-Hill Company, New York (USA), 1937. [Archive.org](#).
- Frank Yates. Contingency Tables Involving Small Numbers and the Chi square Test. *Supplement to the Journal of the Royal Statistical Society*, 1(2):217–235, 1934. ISSN 1466-6162. doi: 10.2307/2983604. [JSTOR](#).

Associated Data**Copyright**

Copyright © March 5, 2023 by Ilija Barukčić, Horandstrasse, Jever, Germany. All Rights Reserved. Alle Rechte vorbehalten.

© 2024 Ilija Barukčić^{a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j, k, l, m} Ilija Barukčić, Chief-Editor, Jever, Germany, March 5, 2023. All rights reserved. Alle Rechte vorbehalten. This is an open access article which can be downloaded under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>).

I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

^a<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6988-2780>

^b<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/1972920>

^c<https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=37099674500>

^d<https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=54974181600>

^e<https://www.mendeley.com/search/?authorFullName=Ilija%20Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87&page=1&query=Barukcic&sortBy=relevance>

^f<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ilija-Barukcic-2>

^g<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87%22&sort=mostviewed>

^h<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87,%20Conference%22>

ⁱ<https://twitter.com/ilijabarukcic?lang=de>

^jhttps://twitter.com/Causation_Journ

^khttps://vixra.org/author/ilija_barukcic

^l<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwf3w1IngcukI00jpw8HTwg>

^m<https://portal.dnb.de/opac/showNextResultSite?currentResultId=%22Barukcic%22%26any¤tPosition=30>